

ELEPHANT

IN THE LAB

SHORT ANALYSIS

Taking care of people – and authorship

Short title	Taking care of people – and authorship
Long title	Bibliometrics for the Subject Areas Dentistry, Health Professions, Nursing, and Psychology for the 20 Highest Performing Authors
Authors	Martin Schmidt ¹ , Benedikt Fecher ¹ , Christian Kobsda ¹
Author affiliation	¹ Knowledge Dimension, Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society, Berlin, Germany
Author bios	<p>Martin Schmidt is a doctoral researcher at the Institute of Landscape Systems Analysis within Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research and associate researcher at Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p> <p>Benedikt Fecher is the programme director of the research programme Knowledge Dimension and heads the Open Science research group at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p> <p>Christian Kobsda works as the political consultant at the Leibniz Association and is an associate researcher at the Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society.</p>
Author social links	Martin Schmidt: ORCID – ResearchGate – Twitter Benedikt Fecher: ORCID – ResearchGate Christian Kobsda: ORCID – ResearchGate – Twitter
Date published	31 July 2017
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.834669
Cite as (APA)	Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Bibliometrics for the Subject Areas Dentistry, Health Professions, Nursing, and Psychology for the 20 Highest Performing Authors. <i>Elephant in the lab</i> . DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.834669

Description

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Dentistry* is 5.5 on average with a maximum of 25 authors. The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.04 per year in the respective time period (Figure 1). The articles in this analysis ($n = 1536$) were cited 13.6 times on average with a maximum of 183 citations.

SHORT ANALYSIS

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA DENTISTRY

Increase of co-authors per year = <0.1
Number of articles = 1536

Figure 1: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Dentistry*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Health Professions* is 3.7 on average with a maximum of 16 authors (Figure 2). The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.1 per year in the respective time period. The articles in this analysis ($n = 808$) were cited 7 times on average and 140 as maximum.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA HEALTH PROFESSIONS

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.1
Number of articles = 808

Figure 2: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Health Professions*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Nursing* is 3.7 on average with a maximum of 61 authors. The mean number of coauthors is decreasing by 0.3 per year in the respective time period (Figure 3). The articles in this analysis ($n = 1282$) were cited 7.5 times on average with a maximum of 126 citations.

SHORT ANALYSIS

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA NURSING

Increase of co-authors per year = 0.3
Number of articles = 1282

Figure 3: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Nursing*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

The number of authors per article in the subject area *Psychology* is 4.1 on average with a maximum of 61 authors (Figure 4). The mean number of coauthors is increasing by 0.05 per year in the respective time period. The articles in this analysis ($n = 954$) were cited 14.4 times on average and 200 as maximum.

NUMBER OF AUTHORS PER ARTICLE IN THE SUBJECT AREA PSYCHOLOGY

Increase of co-authors per year = <0.1
Number of articles = 954

Figure 4: [Boxplot](#) of the number of authors per paper in the subject area *Psychology*. The box denotes 25–75% of the values with the median (bold line) in it. The small circles are outliers. Due to a limitation of the y-axis, some outliers are not shown. The yellow line shows a linear model of the mean number of authors per article with a confidence interval of 0.95 shown in light grey. Data source: Scopus. CC BY 4.0 Schmidt, Fecher, Kobsda.

Methodology

The results of the Advanced search in Scopus were restricted by an algorithm with

- a time period of publishing (2010 to 2016)
- the document types (articles or reviews),

- and a quantitative limitation regarding the publication output (articles by the 20 highest performing authors with the most Scopus listed articles in every subject area).

For details and code see Schmidt et al. [2017](#).

References

Schmidt, M., Fecher, B., Kobsda, C. (2017). Methodology for the analysis of authors using meta data from Scopus. [Elephant in the lab](#). [Link](#).